

SMART PRODUCTS, ENGINEERING AND SERVICES – AN EXAMPLE OF MODERN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

As digitization and Industry 4.0 progress, the need for smart products and innovative business models increases. This contribution presents the underlying novel concept of the collaborative course “Smart Products, Engineering and Services”. The objective is to enable students of mechanical engineering to develop and work with smart products, and to derive possible business models for their use. A combination of traditional lectures, flipped classroom exercises and a development project characterizes the unique character of the course. The presented topics range from the basics of sensing machine elements, intelligent mechatronic systems and the use of artificial intelligence in the latter. Further, it comprises product development methods such as agile development, V&V methods and the usage of rapid

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manufacturing technologies. The flipped classroom exercises serve as preparation for the project work and allow students to gain practical experience with additive manufacturing processes as well as cyber-physical systems. As part of the project work, students develop a smart product which must complete the control task of balancing a body on vertically excited surface by minimizing the bodies movement. For this purpose, the kinematics, the controller, and the usage of a force-measuring ball bearing as a sensing machine element are predetermined. Missing components must be designed and manufactured in a Makerspace using 3D printing or laser cutting and the developed controller must be implemented. The smart product is finally tested on a specially developed test rig.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, an engineer will not be performing the same task throughout his work life. In our fast-paced world, quickly learning and transmitting newly acquired knowledge to team members has become much more important (Castaneda & Cuellar, 2020). It is paramount to know and understand technologies such as AI, Big Data, rapid prototyping etc. in order to grasp the potential and the development implications for new products. Equally important is the ability to manage a team through an environment with limited resources in time, material, and availability of production capacities. Especially with regard to time, rapid prototyping can be leveraged to achieve quick transitions from concept to prototype, thereby accelerating development speed. The new Master's course Smart Products, Engineering and Services (SPES) is held for the first time in 2022. The concept is a response to the growing need for highly versatile engineers that not only dominate their own domain, but in addition show expertise in neighbouring areas. The topics of the lectures range from the basics of smart mechatronic systems and smart machine elements over rapid manufacturing technologies and agile development methods to the application of smart systems for e.g. condition monitoring. Furthermore the lecture covers market analyses and business models in order to discuss and analyse the economic potential of smart products and services. Accompanying the lectures, Flipped-classroom exercises and a complex mechatronic development project subsequently to the lectures are performed in groups of five. The flipped-classroom exercises topics expand the concepts presented in the lectures and facilitate the application of theoretical knowledge throughout the development project. The project itself assists students in the transition from theory-driven university to the industry.

2 METHODOLOGY

The teaching concept integrates the idea of deepening theoretical knowledge gained within the lectures into two student-centered teaching approaches. After conveying the key knowledge in compact lectures during the first five weeks, SPES aims at breaking through the simplifications of a purely theoretical course and confronts students with problematics that arise when working on an engineering problem. Prior to the project work the students can participate in the flipped-classroom exercises as a team. The format incentivises students to prepare their works individually and

present their findings shortly. This enhances communication and presentation skills. As a motivation, a successful participation improves the student's final grade by earning a small bonus. The flipped classroom is a method to teach problem solving skills for more complex tasks. Developed by Bergmann and Sams (2012) for schools and adapted for higher education it flips the traditional way of teaching and learning. Instead of learning the basics in face-to-face classes and reinforcing what they have learned by solving assignments at home, students prepare for a lesson by learning the basics individually. In the lesson itself, the students solve tasks together or discuss the learning content (Werner et al., 2018). Cho et al. (2021) list studies that found various advantages and disadvantages of using flipped classrooms in mechanical engineering teaching. It is shown that the flipped classroom leads to a higher learning success, as long as the number of participants is not too large, or is managed appropriately. With approximately 25 students, the number of students is similar to the size of a school class and is therefore suitable for the Flipped Classroom. The final project phase is accompanied by a limited number of optional helpdesks where students can seek counsel regarding engineering topics. This teaches them to self-identify their weak spots and carefully choose on what questions they need aid. The final grade is based on the written exam at the end of the project phase as well as the evaluation of a written project elaboration and an oral colloquium of the project results. The results of exercises and project work are included into the curriculum to iteratively improve the course for future terms. Doing so the work of participants has a direct influence on the orientation of SPES and aligns the discussed topics to the need of students and the industry.

3 RESULTS

The concept of SPES is based on a review on state-of-the-art teaching methods. Ten lectures convey the basics for the successful realization of a smart product. Lectures about business models, market analysis and acceptance, innovation management, and concepts for generating ideas give an overview to get in touch with methods and the jargon of economics. Additionally, eight lectures cover a wide range of interesting methodologies in growing R&D areas. Core ideas transmitted are implications and methods for developing products in a fast-paced world leveraging available technologies such as rapid prototyping, AI methods, and Big Data. Even most recent research results are introduced to the auditory in order to enable innovative smart products utilizing current research trends were possible, (Reichwein et al., 2020). Up-to-date norms are discussed in the context of the classical V-model for product development as well as agile development.

3.1 Flipped Classroom exercise

The flipped classroom concept encourages students to deepen their knowledge and to train teaching and presentation skills. First, the individual student teams are given a list of tasks, of which they individually choose two tasks, complete them and teach their insights to the other teams within the flipped classroom environment. Research associates as well as student tutors are providing expert knowledge and supervision

during the preparation of the tasks as well as the flipped classroom lectures, to ensure a sufficient quality of the lectures. Necessary fundamentals are taught through traditional lectures as well as supplementary material available online (catalogs, tutorials, scientific articles, etc.). The exercises are intended to deepen the content of the lectures and to prepare students for the practical project phase. Different tasks for every group vary from exercises in the field of 3D printing or programming microcontrollers and on the other hand of a theoretical nature, in which the current state of research is analyzed and discussed. The students have 3 weeks to complete the assignment. For the practical tasks, the Makerspace is available as a place to elaborate the solution. The results are presented by each group to all students and discussed in short presentations. Particularly good or interesting results extend the content of the lectures in subsequent years and enable students to actively contribute to the continuous improvement of the lectures quality as well as the coverage of state-of-the-art topics. The presented topics of the first term varied from rapid manufacturing techniques up to trends in artificial intelligence.

3.2 Project phase

Following the flipped classroom units, the participants develop a smart product, representing a balancing system, which will be field tested in the course of a final presentation. The test environment is a damped two mass oscillator, which represents a quarter car and is shown in figure 1. The students will design parts of the kinematic and manufacture the system using FFF and SLA printers, as well as a laser cutter. For assembly and post processing an open Makerspace including all necessary tools is accessible to the participants. To conduct the control task, the teams have to develop a control strategy, calculate the control parameters and implement the control system using an autonomous calculation unit. The smart product consists of the developed kinematic, predefined sensors and actuators and the controller which is designed and implemented by the students. Sensors are available in the form of displacement and acceleration sensors as well as a sensing rolling bearing as sensing machine element. The sensor data serves as input for the control system as well as for data analysis and the use of artificial intelligence to e.g. predict future behaviour of the test rig.

Fig. 1. Left: A developed smart system, right: Propulsion system of the test rig

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